

SOCIO-ECONOMIC LIFE OF THE RUSSIAN POPULATION RESETTLED IN TURKESTAN

Urmanov Ulug'bek Adkhamjonovich

Fergana State University

Senior teacher of the Department of History of Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7939743>

Abstract: In the article, as a result of the migration policy of the Russian Empire at the end of the 19th - beginning of the 20th century, the Russian-speaking and European peoples who moved to Turkistan were located in places with favorable conditions for cattle breeding, horticulture, policing, and farming, and economic benefits were given to the immigrants. data on the socio-economic life of immigrants with the local population were analyzed.

Key words: Livestock, horse, ox, camel, sheep, goat, press, settlement, Russian-speaking, nomadic herdsman, livestock, village, pasture land, farming, policing, viticulture, horticulture, bedazor, wheat, Molokan.

Due to the fact that many problematic situations arise in the process of resettlement of the population to Turkestan, there was a need to develop special rules and regulations in this area by the government of the empire. For these reasons, many articles were published in the periodical press discussing questions such as whether there is suitable land for the immigrants to farm in the country, what principles and rules are used to build the settlements in Turkestan, how the displaced people are adapting to the new natural, climatic and economic conditions.

"Turkestan collection" and periodical press have published articles and reports on the fact that the government could not always control the movement of those who go to Turkistan "in search of happiness", that they are sentenced to death and starvation, and that it is the right way to return such people to the Motherland, although there are only a few shows that there are different opinions. They stayed among the local population, whose beliefs, traditions, and economic traditions are long, and although they live half-starved, there were many who considered the need to return to their country desirable.

It is worth noting that the imperial government spent a lot of effort to control and regulate the resettlement process. After 1892, the voluntary migration of the Russian-speaking population to Turkestan increased. Over the years, the work of managing the resettlement of the population to Turkestan was carried out by the ministries and various agencies of the Russian Empire, as well as by local authorities. The establishment of Russian-speaking villages and settlements, the control of farms in them was initially under the jurisdiction of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the imperial government, and the responsibility of studying and reporting on new population centers was assigned to the "special commissions" created by the Turkestan Governor General. Later, the control of resettlement works was transferred to the Ministry of Agriculture and Land Affairs.

In 1869, academician V.V. Barthold provides information. According to this regulation, it belongs to the Cossacks who were relocated in the Ettisuv and Syrdarya regions, and each male member of the family was allocated up to 30 desiatins of land. By 1886, this rate was

reduced to 7.7 deciles. However, as the displaced military Cossacks moved away from agriculture and engaged in fishing and boating, the relief fund was reduced. Before the Regulation of 1869, each military Cossack household was allocated an average of 100 decitas of land for cultivation and cattle raising. S. N. Brezhnova also touched on this Regulation in her research. In our opinion, one of the goals of this Regulation was to encourage the Cossacks to engage in agriculture, and thereby to encourage the local population to move from nomadic animal husbandry to a settled life. Because it was very convenient for the colonial administration to manage the settled population.

In many cases, the local population did not want to fulfill the requirements of this Regulation, they considered the territories transferred to the state land fund as vacant land to be theirs. This is also confirmed by the information on the pages of the periodical press. In some newspapers, "the life of the nomads is militarized, the Kyrgyz clans are not afraid of conflict with the government, they believe that "where my horse's hoof touches, that is the land that belongs to me", Kyrgyz graze their camels and horses, herds of sheep and goats without knowing the boundaries and camp wherever they want. The fact that "it keeps on sewing" is also evidenced by this. Маҳаллий аҳоли томонидан норозиликнинг кучайиб бориши, ички вазиятнинг кескинлашуви ҳукуматни ён беришга мажбур қилди. Натижада, 1886 йилдаги Низом талабларини тақиқловчи, Туркистонга деҳқонларнинг кўчиб жойлашишига қарши буйруқни Туркистон генерал-губернатори С.Вревский имзолади.

In 1881, 24 families of German Mennonites and 50 families of Molokans moved to the village of Koplonbek near Tashkent. Molokans, like the German Mennonites, went into conflict with the leadership to demand military service and freedom and rights. At the time of the establishment of resettled settlements in the steppe desert, there were 40 families of Molokans on 53 tens of acres of land. They quickly set up their farm by moving with some money, livestock, 1-prong plow, and work animals (horses, oxen). In the village of Molokans, there was a school with 40 students and a church where the residents prayed. Among them, 12 families were especially wealthy, and they owned fortresses, orchards, fields of vegetable and polizi crops, and bed gardens. In 1906-1909, on average, 50-70 pounds of wheat were obtained from each hectare of land. However, these lands were confiscated by the government in 1910 because the Molokans refused to pay conscription taxes. Molokans demanded their legal rights and appealed to the government with applications and complaints about the 10-year lease of these lands. After their appeals were not resolved positively, the Molokans moved to Pishpek district of Ettisuv region. Only 35 of them lived in the Dasht desert.

According to the sources, 450 German Mennonites and Molokans were located in Masalsky and Saratovsky settlements in the south-east of Garmot district in Kaspiyorti region in 1889-1896. Molokans mainly immigrated from the Caucasus and engaged in agriculture and animal husbandry. They brought sheep with soft wool to the country with them. In addition to planting grain crops such as wheat, barley, millet, and oats, the Molokans also engaged in horticulture, viticulture, cattle and sheep breeding, hunting, and even floriculture. In 1897-1906, they were the first to introduce modern agricultural machinery (plough, mower, harrow, harrow) in Masalsky and Saratovsky settlements.

Molokans had prosperous settlements. In 1894, 14 Baptists and 6 Molokans founded the village of Kurapakino, 25 miles from Ashgabat, near the Annau Ovuli of the Turkmen, Annau River. Later, it reached 83 households with those who moved from Kars, Kuban,

Stavropol, Tambov, Kherson, Samara provinces. In the settlement of Molokanlar, there was a plantation of vine seedlings on an area of 40 kilometers, each farm had 2 tens of irrigated land, and 3 thousand tens of pasture land for livestock. A dairy farm was established in Molokans. They had 200 milch cows and took their goods to the Ashgabat market and sold them mainly to military garrisons. They have also made significant progress in cattle breeding. They established a horse breeding farm, crossed their own horses with the thoroughbred horses of Ashgabat, and founded new horse breeds. They created orchards and grape plantations. New varieties of flowers (siren, rose, jasmine) were cultivated and brought to the markets for sale. Molokans also produced marketable products in areas such as winemaking and poultry farming.

Molokans also lived in Alekseevka settlement of Shymkent district of Syrdarya region. They immigrated from Yerevan (Armenia) in 1907 as 57 families. It is stated in the sources that displaced Molokans are hardworking, orderly, disciplined, enterprising, well-educated people who manage their farms wisely. Molokans also tried their luck in cotton, rice, and other areas of irrigated agriculture. However, keeping sheep, goats, cattle and poultry in them gave the expected result. In horticulture, they organized a model farm in viticulture and floriculture.

In historical sources, it is noted that in the Russian-speaking settlements, every family's house was surrounded by wire mesh and bricks. In front of the residential buildings there is a garden with special seats (benches), a flower garden, fruit and decorative trees, a courtyard with an area of 5-7 sajen (1 sajen - 2.16 meters), a storehouse (sklad) for storing food, a shed for livestock. (palace), it is noted that there was an area of land where vegetables and rice crops were planted.

The Russian government encouraged immigrants of different nationalities to settle in one place. Among those who moved, the economic situation of the population, who had farm animals and working tools, improved rapidly. Rich information about the life of peasants in exemplary Russian-speaking villages and settlements located in the uyezds of the Syrdarya, Kaspiyorti, Fergana, Samarkand regions in the sources is the basis for us to express the above opinion. Schools were built at the expense of the government in Kazansky and Mishensky villages of Tashkent uezd of Syrdarya region, and in the 1st and 2nd Blagoveshchensky villages of Osh uezd of Fergana region.

All the schools in 5 German Mennonite villages in Avliyoota uezd of Syrdarya region and Tashkent uezd were built at the expense of the village community, and the school desks and chairs were made by German Mennonite craftsmen. Children of German Mennonites studied subjects such as German, arithmetic, geography, and Russian at school. They mainly acquired the basics of primary education and learned to engage in crafts, farming, animal husbandry, horticulture, vegetable growing, and policing activities from the experience of adults. German Mennonites were sent textbooks and newspapers through German Mennonites in the United States.

In general, the everyday life of the population relocated to Turkestan, the relations between the Russian-speaking population and the local peoples: Kyrgyz (Kazakhs are called this in the sources-diss.), Karakyrghyz (Kyrgyz), Uzbeks (Sarts) were not always smooth, there were conflicts over land and water issues, their origin the reasons for its appearance are interpreted differently by the authors. The fact that the authors of some articles and messages

tried to evaluate the causes of mutual conflicts, disagreements and conflicts as objectively as possible indicates that these sources are important and reliable.

In short, the people who moved to Turkestan settled in places with favorable conditions for farming and economically restored themselves, gave Turkestan such definitions as "river of milk", "honey shore", "lively land", supporting Turkestan and encouraging the population. migration was promoted and encouraged. Residents from dozens of governorates of the Russian Empire were moved to Turkestan, along with German Mennonites, Caucasians from the Caucasus, Kars, Ardagan, Botumi, and Yerevan. Uyghurs, Dungans, and Taranists were brought to the country from East Turkestan and settled. Turks, Hungarians, Romanians, Poles, Germans, and Austrians who were captured during the First World War were also transferred to the regions of the country. Conflicts between displaced population and local population on land and water issue, some of the migrants involved in horse and ox theft, addiction to alcohol, smoking and prostitution had a negative impact on the socio-psychological condition of the local population.

Two different approaches to resettlement policy were formed at that time. By observing the periodical press materials, we can see that despite the critical aspects of some articles, the resettlement policy is mostly justified and supported in most articles. The relocation was mainly explained by the need to ensure the security of the Russian Empire, to strengthen the borders, to solve the demographic problems in the metropolis, to protect the "state interests" in the country, and to absorb the wealth of Turkestan. The idea of turning Turkestan into an "integral part of the Russian Empire" through the resettlement policy was put forward.

References:

- 1.Urmonov U. Role Of Livestock And Livestock Products In Domestic And Foreign Trade Of The Ferghana Valley (Late XIX-Beginning Of XX Century): <https://doi.org/10.47100/Conferences.V1i1.1261>. Inresearch Support Center Conferences 2021 Aug 18 (No. 18.05).
- 2.Urmonov U. The role of livestock and products in domestic and foreign trade of Turkestan in the late XIX and early XX centuries. Electronic journal of actual problems of modern science, education and training. -January, 2022-I. ISSN 2181-9750, 2022-yil.
- 3.Urmonov U. Turkistonda chorvachilikning aholi kundalik hayotidagi o'rni. Qarshi davlat universiteti. Sohibqiron yulduzi. -4-son, 2021-yil.
- 4.Urmonov U.A. Recourses Of Livestock In Tukistan In The Late XIX Century-Early XX Century: Comparative Analysis. – The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations (ISSN – 2689-100x) Published: November 30, – 2020. 491-495 p.
- 5.A.K. Русские переселенцы в Туркестан // Туркестанский сборник. Том 586. –С. 201. Колонизационные значение Туркестана// Туркестанский курьер, 1906. №210.
- 6.Бартольд В.В. История культурной жизни Туркестана. Ленинград. Издательство Академии наук СССР. 1927. – С.148-149; Велецкий. Положение переселенческого дела в Семиречиньской области // Туркестанские ведомости. 1907. №133;134.
- 7.Брежнева С.Н. Отражение идеи аккультурации в переселенческой политике Российской империи в Туркестане на рубеже XIX–XX вв. // Вестник РУДН. Серия: ИСТОРИЯ РОССИИ. 2018. Т. 17. № 3. – С. 608–638.

8. Валерий Правдив. Роль русской колонизации. // Туркестанские ведомости. 1907. –№ 132. Русский о колонизации Туркестана. // Туркестанский сборник. Том 425. – С.48. Несколько слов о переселение в Сыр-Дарьинской области. // Среднеазиатская жизнь. 1907.– № 184-185.
- 9.История русской колонизации Туркестана. // Туркестанский сборник. Том 586. – С.15-16; Колобов М. Молоканство в Туркестан растёт. // Туркестанский сборник. Том 492. – С. 181-183; Тилгаев К. Богарные земли. // Туркестанский курьер.1909.– № 98; Молоканство. // Туркестанские ведомости.1916 – № 196.
- 10.Колонизационное значение Туркестана // Торгово–промышленная газета. 1906. №210.
- 11.Молоканство в Туркестан растёт. // Туркестанский сборник. Том 492. – С.183
- 12.Наша колонизация в Средней Азии. // Туркестанский сборник. Том 429. – С.231; Антонович. Переселенческая задача. // Туркестанский курьер, 1908. –№ 35.
- 13.Сибирь и Туркестан. // Ташкентский курьер, 1906. – № 40; Тилгаев К. Богарные земли. // Туркестанский курьер, 1905, – № 98, По поводу стопрочных путей в Семиречье. // Туркестанские ведомости. 1907. – № 79; Наша колонизация в Средней Азии. // Туркестанский сборник. Том. 429. – С.335.
- 14.Туркестанец. К.вопросу о колонизации Туркестанского края. // Туркестанский сборник. Том. 429. – С. 111.
- 15.Ўзбекистон Миллий Архиви И-36-фонд, 1-рўйхат, 3279–йиғма жилд, 9-варақ.

